

Odor-memory retrieval in *Drosophila* requires a state of arousal

Stanislav Ott¹, Xianyuan Zhang¹, Tayfun Tumkaya^{1,2}, James Charles Stewart^{1,2}, Adam Claridge-Chang^{1,2,3,4}

1. Program in Neuroscience and behavioral Disorders, Duke-NUS Medical School, Singapore
2. Institute for Molecular and Cell Biology, A*STAR, Singapore
3. Department of Physiology, National University of Singapore, Singapore
4. Correspondence: claridge-chang.adam@duke-nus.edu.sg

Abstract

The mechanisms of how arousal affects learning and memory are insufficiently understood. We investigated how olfactory memory retrieval in *Drosophila* is affected by the arousal state of the animal and found that learned odor avoidance is dependent on mechanical agitation. Without mechanical agitation, flies store the aversive memory, but do not exhibit this aversion during testing. In the presence of agitation, inhibition of several mechanosensor classes abolished recall. Conversely, in the absence of agitation, activated peripheral mechanosensors restored shock-odor memory recall. These results establish that arousal-dependent retrieval requires, and is induced by, activation of mechanosensors. A screen of CNS mechanosensory drivers identified a specific cluster of interneurons that were required and instructive for memory retrieval. In the brain, a mushroom-body dopamine cluster is required for agitation-dependent memory retrieval, in conjunction with mechanosensory neuron activation. These studies highlight the relevance of arousal in memory, and describe new roles for dopamine, and peripheral and central mechanosensors in the expression of olfactory memory.

Introduction

Arousal is described as a general state of the central nervous system with high arousal levels being associated with alertness, heightened perception, and characteristic patterns of brain activity¹⁻³. However, multiple states can be described by 'arousal'² and distinct forms of arousal that are relevant for different types of behaviors have been reported⁴⁻⁶. The overall arousal level of an animal depends on its physiological state (endogenous arousal) and the environmental stimuli (exogenous arousal)⁷. While the effects of endogenous arousal on memory storage have been documented⁸⁻¹⁰, the role of exogenous arousal in learning and memory remains poorly understood. To address this question, we have examined how arousal modulates learned behavior with the *Drosophila* olfactory conditioning paradigm.

Activity is considered to be a general reporter of arousal state in *Drosophila*, with high levels of activity indicating high levels of arousal¹¹. Arousal has been shown to be critically important for a range of fly behaviors, such as courtship¹², the sleep/wake cycle^{13,14} and aggression¹⁵. The arousal state of *Drosophila* appears to be primarily regulated by dopamine and different perturbations of dopamine signaling have been shown to affect sleep and overall activity^{4,11,16,17}. The involvement of other monoamines in arousal is less clear. Studies suggest that octopamine and histamine generally promote activity¹⁸⁻²⁰, whereas serotonin appears to promote quiescence²¹. Furthermore, it has been established that dopamine, octopamine and serotonin are required for associative learning in *Drosophila*²²⁻²⁵ but the role of histamine in this context is not well understood^{26,27}. While the instructive effects of dopamine on sensory cues are well studied²⁸, its role in eliciting additional arousal-relevant stimuli during conditioning is unclear.

Besides regulating activity, arousal has also been reported to mediate selective attention^{1,29,30} that is required to actively attend to a sensory cue in higher organisms³¹. In *Drosophila*, selective attention to visual cues has primarily been studied during tethered flight^{29,32} or as a response to a visual threat^{5,33,34}. Interestingly, classical learning mutants such as *dunce*, *rutabaga*, and *radish*^{35,36} display hyperactivity phenotypes, indicating that attention and learning deficits are related. In rodents and humans, emotional arousal promotes long term memory via stress hormone release⁸, thus revealing a link between the internal state of the organism and memory consolidation. Overall, these observations suggest that arousal and attention could be critical components of *Drosophila* olfactory conditioning, and changes in arousal levels such as those induced through changes in the conditioning protocol could alter conditioned outcomes.

In nearly all conditioning paradigms, the study subject is inadvertently exposed to external stimuli from the environment. In *Drosophila*, a majority of memory studies to date have been conducted by using the olfactory T-maze³⁷. This assay involves the transfer of flies between chambers, potentially exposing them to light, sound and mechanical agitation, all of which could alter the animal's arousal levels and potentially impact the outcome of the experiment. Despite the large body of discoveries stemming from the use of the T-maze (reviewed in³⁸), the impact of external arousal on conditioned odor avoidance has not been investigated. By analyzing the effects of exogenous arousal during the aversive shock-odor

conditioning paradigm, we have found that the T-maze chamber transfer is required for the display of odor memory.

To overcome limitations of the T-maze design, we developed a multi-fly olfactory trainer (MOT) platform that enabled us to observe the behavior of groups of flies during conditioning. We show that arousal represents a key component of the olfactory conditioning protocol. Throughout classical conditioning flies learn the aversiveness of the shock-associated odor but do not display strong avoidance in the absence of an arousing stimulus. Strong avoidance was only observed after *Drosophila* became aroused, either through mechanosensation or other arousing stimuli. In the absence of agitation, *Drosophila* remained largely stationary and indifferent to the shock-odor. Subjecting flies to agitation increased their activity and elicited shock-odor avoidance, which then remained high for the duration of the testing period. Agitation is not the only means by which strong odor avoidance can be achieved. Increasing endogenous arousal via starvation leads to increased shock-odor avoidance independently of agitation.

By using optogenetics, we identify mechanosensory neurons as being required and sufficient for the display of high shock-odor avoidance. Optogenetic activation of distinct subsets of mechanosensitive neurons, that are normally stimulated by leg bristles,³⁹ was sufficient to elicit memory in the absence of external arousal. Optogenetic inhibition of these neurons impaired shock-odor avoidance even after agitation. In the brain, the dopaminergic cluster of PAM neurons was found to be partially required for shock-odor avoidance. Optogenetic inhibition of broad PAM subsets, or those that specifically project to the $\beta'2$ region of the *Drosophila* MB, strongly impaired shock-odor avoidance. Odor avoidance induction via mechanosensory neurons was less effective in the presence of PAM inhibition, suggesting that both components could be part of the same arousal induction pathway. Taken together, these studies highlight the importance of arousal for aversive olfactory conditioning and provide a framework for further enquiries into arousal-mediated behaviors.

Results

Odor-avoidance memory in the T-maze requires the elevator transfer

The classic T-maze assay uses separate training and testing chambers between which the flies are conveyed by an elevator (Figure 1A)³⁷. We aimed to simplify this protocol by training and testing flies in a single chamber, a protocol we termed 'No change'.

Surprisingly, flies in the No change protocol did not display conditioned avoidance (Figure 1B, 1D). To determine which aspects of the Classic T-maze protocol were needed for a high memory score, we examined whether performance using a single train/test chamber could be improved by adding an intervening elevator transfer (Figure 1C). Such a 'Circulated' procedure, in which flies were trained and tested in the same tubes, produced high performance (Figure 1D); this suggested that conditioned avoidance in the T-maze requires one or more sensory features of the elevator transfer. To isolate the required sensory modality, we implemented a version of the Circulated protocol that used a quiet, padded T-maze in the dark: this elicited high performance (Figure 1E, second column). Conversely, a version of the No change protocol (Figure 1B) that added both the sound stimulus of

T-maze tapping and the room light stimulus associated with an elevator transfer resulted in poor performance (Figure 1E, third column). These results suggest that visual and auditory cues are not critical for T-maze performance, and that conditioned flies require mechanosensory stimulation prior to olfactory-avoidance testing.

Shaking can substitute for T-maze elevator transfer

We hypothesized that flies trained in the No change protocol had normal learning, and that post-training mechanical agitation would improve performance, thus revealing an otherwise cryptic memory. After training with the No change protocol, we tested the flies twice: once before (pre-agitation test) and once after agitating (post-agitation test) the T-maze by shaking and tapping. As before, the No change flies showed poor performance (Figure 1G, first column). However, the same flies displayed high performance after agitation, comparable to the other protocols, thus verifying the hypothesis (Figure 1G, second column). High performance was also observed when the T-maze was shaken after a 45-min delay (Figure 1G, third column). These results indicate that flies subjected to the No change protocol learn normally, but that mechanical agitation is required for the behavioral expression of stored memory.

Figure 1. Olfactory memory in the T-maze requires pre-test agitation.

A. Schematic of the key steps of the Classic T-maze protocol. Flies are trained at the top of the T-maze in a chamber with a copper shock grid. After training, they are tapped into the

elevator and lowered to a middle position. Two chambers are attached to the lower ports and the elevator is pushed to release the flies at the choice point. **B.** The No change T-maze protocol: flies are trained and tested at the lower position. **C.** The Circulated protocol: after training, the flies are tapped into one chamber which is moved to the top port. Flies are tapped into the elevator and tested as per the classic protocol. **D.** Memory performance indices (PI) in the Classic, No change, and Circulated protocols. Upper panels show experimental iterations (dots) and PI (bars); lower panels show mean differences (black dots, Δ PI) with their sampling-error curves. Classic $n = 222$ flies over 3 experimental iterations. No change $n = 249$ flies over 3 experimental iterations. Circulated $n = 293$ flies over 3 experimental iterations. **E.** Comparison of results from the three protocols: Circulated, Quiet–Dark Circulated, and No change with sound and light. Circulated $n = 279$ flies over 3 experimental iterations. Quiet–Dark Circulated $n = 255$ flies over 3 experimental iterations. No change with sound and light $n = 284$ flies over 3 experimental iterations. **F.** Otherwise identical to the No change protocol, the Shaking protocol adds mechanical agitation prior to testing. **G.** PI (upper) and Δ PI (lower) for No change, Shake, and delayed Shake protocols. No change $n = 292$ flies over 3 experimental iterations. Shaken $n = 281$ flies over 3 experimental iterations. Shaken with 45 min delay $n = 283$ flies over 3 experimental iterations. Error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. Additional statistics are presented in Supplementary Table [ST1](#).

Memory performance also requires agitation in an automated assay

To generalize these findings, we conducted agitation tests in multi-fly olfactory trainers (MOT1 and MOT2, Figure 2A) that measure olfactory memory in small groups of flies^{22,40,41}. As in the T-maze, conditioning in the MOTs without agitation resulted in only weak performance (Figure 2B, C). When retested after agitation, the performance of MOT-conditioned flies improved substantially. This was true for chambers knocked manually (MOT1, data not shown) or by air-puff agitation (MOT2, Figure 2C, D, E). As in the T-maze, light and sound stimuli that mimicked those occurring during chamber tapping were ineffective at increasing memory performance (Supplementary Figure S1A, B). Post-agitation memory was also not formed by anosmic *Orco*¹ flies⁴² (Supplementary Figure S1C). Thus, the dependence of memory performance on mechanical agitation is generalizable to at least two different olfactory-conditioning formats.

Figure 2: Agitation is also required for memory expression in an automated assay,
A. Schematic of the MOT2 conditioning assay. The apparatus allows the control of odor, agitating air puffs, electric shock, and optogenetic illumination; flies are imaged with infrared back-illumination. Additional information is given in the methods section. **B.** Diagram of an anti-OCT conditioning protocol. Fly odor preference is assayed three times: bias check, pre-agitation test and post-agitation test. The timings of the odors (top), shock (middle) and agitation (bottom) stimuli are shown. During the bias check and tests, flies are presented a choice between two different odors (MCH and OCT). **C.** Average PI over experimental time. Shock-odor avoidance was poor during the pre-agitation test, but

increased substantially after air-puff agitation test. **D.** Average walking speed of *Drosophila* throughout the training regime (same flies as in C). For C-D n = 888 flies over 74 experimental iterations. **E.** Data from a single chamber (a subset of the data above) showing coordinates of six flies throughout an experiment. Error ribbons in C and D show the 95% CI. Additional statistics are presented in Supplementary Table [ST1](#).

Mechanical agitation increases walking speed during memory recall test

Walking speed has previously been used as an indicator of overall arousal levels, for the assessment of sleep/wake states^{43–45} and for agitation-elicited activity responses^{4,5}. In our experiments, walking speed was highly variable throughout a typical MOT2 conditioning cycle (Figure 2D). After loading the flies into the conditioning chambers, the average walking speed was relatively high at about 5 mm/s. The speed declined to about 1 mm/s during the odor-bias check and remained low until the start of the training epochs. During shock training, the speed increased to ~3 mm/s, and the speed bursts were synchronized with the shock pulses. Subsequently, the speed declined to <1 mm/s and remained low until the post-agitation test (Figure 2D). During the pre-agitation test, the flies were indifferent to the shock-paired odor, however, they moved away from the shock-odor area immediately after air-puff agitation (Figure 2C). An example of position coordinates from six flies shows an extreme case (Figure 2E, Supplementary video [V1](#)) in which all flies were located in the shock-paired odor area during pre-agitation test, but moved away from the shock-paired odor during post-agitation test. These results show that the agitation-evoked increase in aversive memory expression occurs simultaneously with an acute, transient increase in walking speed (Figure 2B-E).

Hunger improves recall

We asked if memory performance could be improved by a non-mechanosensory stimulus. Prior studies have shown that hunger promotes foraging behavior, including increased walking¹⁸, visual learning^{18,46} and olfactory learning^{47,48}, and could therefore be a candidate stimulus that might increase the arousal state needed for recall. We asked whether hungry flies (without agitation) had improved memory performance. After 18-h starvation, unagitated shock-odor avoidance remained poor (data not shown). However, when the starvation period was extended to 44 hrs, unagitated performance improved; in the pre-agitation test, hungry flies showed better performance (Δ PI = +0.27) than fed flies (Supplementary Figure S1D). This was not due to improved overall learning in hungry flies, as their post-agitation performance was inferior compared to fed flies and did not increase much relative to the pre-agitation test (Supplementary Figure S1D-E). Starvation did not affect the fly's post-agitation locomotor performance (Supplementary Figure S1F). These results suggest that starvation renders the flies less responsive to agitation and/or lowers their learning capacity, while hunger-related arousal improves unagitated memory performance.

Supplementary Figure 1. Unagitated memory performance is improved by hunger but is not affected by sound or light

A–B. Exposure to 30 s of MOT1-chamber tapping sound (A) or 30 s ambient light (B) did not substantially improve memory performance in the absence of agitation. A $n = 120$ flies over 10 experimental iterations, B $n = 120$ flies over 10 experimental iterations. **C.** In MOT2, olfactory-deficient *Orco*¹ mutants showed poor performance even after agitation, $n = 72$ flies over 6 experimental iterations per respective genotype. **D.** Flies starved on agarose for 44 h prior to conditioning showed increased performance during the pre-agitation test. The schematic on top depicts the stimuli and testing sequences. The 30-s interval shaded in gray indicates the epoch used to calculate the Δ PI contrast (axis on the right). The performance of hungry flies increased by Δ PI = +0.27. **E.** The PI values of control (sated) and starved flies before and after agitation (above); and the agitation effects of the two groups (below). Agitation did not improve the performance of starved flies. **F.** Speed comparisons between sated and hungry flies. Controls $n = 324$ flies over 27 experimental iterations, starved $n = 264$ flies over 22 experimental iterations for panels D–F. Same data was used for analyses in panels D–F. All error ribbons and bars show the 95% CI. Additional statistics are given in Supplementary Table [ST1](#).

Optogenetic manipulation of higher order brain regions associated with arousal does not alter shock-odor avoidance

We aimed to identify the input circuitry for agitation-induced arousal. To this end, we performed two screens where we optogenetically manipulated different neuronal subsets during testing. For neuronal activation, we used CsChrimson (Chr)⁴⁹ and subjected the flies to a 3 s stimulus of red light immediately before pre-agitation testing. We hypothesized that brief optogenetic activation of candidate neurons should be sufficient to recapitulate the odor avoidance and locomotor responses that we previously observed in wild type animals after agitation. For neuronal inhibition, we used GtACR1 (ACR)⁴⁰ and subjected the flies to

green light during agitation and the initial 5 s of post-agitation testing. We speculated that optogenetic silencing of candidate neurons would impair the increase in post-agitation shock-odor avoidance that was observed in wild type animals. For screen candidate selection, we focused on neurons that have been previously implicated in mechanotransduction, rest, food motivation and dopamine signaling. Any candidate driver lines that showed paralysis or gait abnormalities during optogenetic actuation were removed from further analyses. Manipulating neurons previously implicated in food-related motivation⁴⁷, rest⁵⁰ or social interactions⁵¹ did not change conditioned shock-odor avoidance. Furthermore, targeting the ring neurons of the ellipsoid body⁵² with *R56H10-G4*, neurons in the antennal mechanosensory motor center (AMMC)⁵³ with *R65A11-G4* (Figure S2C), fan-shaped body neurons with *R23E10-G4* (Figure S2H)⁵⁴ or giant fiber neurons in the ventral nerve cord (VNC)⁵⁵ with *R24H07-G4* also did not change conditioned odor avoidance (Figure 3A and E). These data indicate that manipulation of higher order brain regions that are associated with mechanosensory processing does not impact arousal-induced shock-odor avoidance.

Optogenetic manipulation of mechanosensory neurons modulates conditioned odor avoidance

The biggest changes in conditioned odor avoidance were observed by manipulating mechanosensory neurons captured by either *Nanchung-G4* (Nan) or *NompC-G4* driver lines (Figure 3A, D). Together with Inactive, *NompC*^{56,57} and *Nanchung*⁵⁸ are thought to play a critical role in auditory signal transduction and the perception of touch^{58–60}. To confirm the screen results we repeated the *Nan-G4>ACR* experiment and tested the flies first in the absence of light and then re-tested the same flies after light actuation. The post-agitation shock-odor avoidance of *Nan-G4>ACR* flies and genotypic controls was similar in the absence of light. However, after light actuation the post-agitation odor avoidance of *Nan-G4>ACR* flies was essentially abolished, while avoidance in control flies remained high (Figure 3B-C). Although the *Nan-G4>ACR* flies were relatively active before light exposure, ACR actuation decreased their activity below the activity levels of control flies for the remainder of the experiment (Figure 3D). Repeating the *Nan-G4>Chr* experiment confirmed that brief activation of *Nan* neurons was sufficient to partially rescue pre-agitation shock-odor avoidance (Figure 3F-G) and to acutely increase locomotion (Figure 3H). The expression patterns of *NompC-G4* and *Nan-G4* primarily overlap in the AMMC⁵³ and some parts of the ventral nerve cord (VNC) (Figure S2A and E). Because manipulating neurons in the AMMC area with other driver lines did not alter shock-odor avoidance, we hypothesized that the arousal-relevant neurons could be located in the VNC.

Figure 3: Optogenetic manipulation of mechanosensory neurons in the VNC modulates conditioned odor avoidance

A. Summary of the arousal inhibition screen. ACR actuation was performed during agitation and 5s afterwards. Each dot in the top plot shows the averaged PI per iteration. The bottom

plot shows the mean difference (ΔPI) between the respective genotypic controls and test. The strongest effects were observed with the driver lines *Nan-G4*, *R18G08-G4* and *R13D11-G4*. Error bars are 95% CI. *Nan-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 240 flies over 20 experimental iterations. *Nan-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 144 flies over 12 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 648 flies over 54 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 468 flies over 39 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 648 flies over 54 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 468 flies over 39 experimental iterations. *R69C05-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 192 flies over 16 experimental iterations. *R69C05-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 420 flies over 35 experimental iterations. *Kras-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 108 flies over 9 experimental iterations. *Kras-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 108 flies over 9 experimental iterations. *R65A11-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 240 flies over 20 experimental iterations. *R65A11-G4-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 432 flies over 36 experimental iterations. *R41E11-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 96 flies over 8 experimental iterations. *R41E11-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 156 flies over 13 experimental iterations. *R24H07-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 216 flies over 18 experimental iterations. *R24H07-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 108 flies over 9 experimental iterations. *TH-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 108 flies over 9 experimental iterations. *TH-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 120 flies over 10 experimental iterations. *23e10-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 144 flies over 12 experimental iterations. *23e10-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 132 flies over 11 experimental iterations. *R56H10-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 168 flies over 14 experimental iterations. *R56H10-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 156 flies over 13 experimental iterations. *c061-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 120 flies over 10 experimental iterations. *c061-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 120 flies over 10 experimental iterations. *R13D11-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 216 flies over 18 experimental iterations. *R13D11-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 384 flies over 32 experimental iterations. *R55B01-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 96 flies over 8 experimental iterations. *R55B01-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 96 flies over 8 experimental iterations. *NPF-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 132 flies over 11 experimental iterations. *NPF-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 132 flies over 11 experimental iterations. **B-D.** Optogenetic inhibition with *Nan-G4*>*ACR* impaired post-agitation avoidance. Shock-odor avoidance was tested twice - first in the absence of opsin actuation (Test) and then again after ACR was activated (post-agitation retest, see schematic on top, B). Post-agitation shock-odor avoidance of *Nan-G4*>*ACR* flies was strongly impaired after opsin actuation (C). *Nan-G4*>*ACR* flies were more active than controls throughout the experiment. However, their speed was lower than the speed of controls during and after opsin actuation (D). The same data was used for analysis in panels B-D. *Nan-G4*>*ACR1* test n = 180 flies over 15 experimental iterations. *Nan-G4*>*ACR1* controls n = 588 flies over 49 experimental iterations. **E.** A summary of the arousal induction screen. Each driver was crossed to express the channelrhodopsin *Chr* and flies were exposed to a 3s light pulse immediately before testing. The strongest effects were observed with the driver lines *NompC-G4*, and *R18G08-G4*. The panel shows the ΔPI effect size distributions for test vs controls with a 95% CI. *Kras-G4*>*Chr* test n = 60 flies over 5 experimental iterations. *Kras-G4*>*Chr* controls n = 72 flies over 6 experimental iterations. *R41E11-G4*>*Chr* test n = 120 flies over 10 experimental iterations. *R41E11-G4*>*Chr* controls n = 96 flies over 8 experimental iterations. *TH-G4*>*Chr* test n = 144 flies over 12 experimental iterations. *TH-G4*>*Chr* controls n = 84 flies over 7 experimental iterations. *c061-G4*>*Chr* test n = 276 flies over 23 experimental iterations.

c061-G4>Chr controls n = 204 flies over 17 experimental iterations. *R13D11-G4>Chr* test n = 336 flies over 28 experimental iterations. *R13D11-G4>Chr* controls n = 312 flies over 26 experimental iterations. *R65A11-G4>Chr* test n = 180 flies over 15 experimental iterations. *R65A11-G4>Chr* controls n = 396 flies over 33 experimental iterations. *R24H07-G4>Chr* test n = 144 flies over 12 experimental iterations. *R24H07-G4>Chr* controls n = 156 flies over 13 experimental iterations. *Nan-G4>Chr* test n = 192 flies over 16 experimental iterations. *Nan-G4>Chr* controls n = 96 flies over 8 experimental iterations. *R69C05-G4>Chr* test n = 408 flies over 34 experimental iterations. *R69C05-G4>Chr* controls n = 216 flies over 18 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4>Chr* test n = 528 flies over 44 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4>Chr* controls n = 300 flies over 25 experimental iterations. *NompC-G4>Chr* test n = 216 flies over 18 experimental iterations. *NompC-G4>Chr* controls n = 168 flies over 14 experimental iterations. **F-H.** Optogenetic activation of neurons captured by *Nan-G4* improved shock-odor avoidance in the absence of agitation. Compared to genotypic controls, the performance of *Nan-G4>Chr* flies was $\Delta\text{PI} = +0.15$ higher in the absence of agitation. Optogenetic activation of *Nan-G4* neurons induced an acute locomotor response (H). For F-H *Nan-G4>Chr* test n = 252 flies over 21 experimental iterations. *Nan-G4>Chr* controls n = 384 flies over 32 experimental iterations. The same data was used for analyses in panels F-H. Additional statistics are presented in Supplementary Table [ST1](#).

Figure S2: Expression patterns of key driver lines used in the arousal screen

Expression pattern of selected driver lines from the optogenetic arousal screens (Figure 3). Imaging was performed under the same settings, all panels show maximum intensity projections. ACR-eYFP expression is shown in green and anti-DLG is shown in magenta. For each panel $n = 1$ brain over 1 experimental iteration.

Manipulation of leg sensilla neurons is sufficient to elicit and impair arousal-induced shock-odor avoidance

Besides *NompC-G4* and *Nan-G4*, the driver lines *R18G08-G4* and *R69C05-G4* produced the strongest results in the arousal screens (Figure 3A and E). Both drivers capture neurons that receive direct input from leg bristles³⁹ and are thus situated very early in the mechanotransduction cascade. Leg bristle actuation has also recently been shown to induce locomotor behavior without the involvement of higher order brain circuitry⁶¹. A previous study has shown that mechanosensory stimulation of *Drosophila* legs is initially detected by leg bristles, which then relay the signal to the VNC³⁹. At the VNC, the signal is processed by three classes of second order neurons that we have tested in our screens.

The first class of neurons compares touch stimuli across contralateral legs and is captured by the driver line *R18G08-G4* (Figure S2G). Optogenetic activation of *R18G08-G4* with Chr almost fully rescued conditioned odor avoidance and substantially increased locomotion in the absence of agitation (Figure 4A-C). To verify that shock-odor avoidance was not affected in the absence of stimulation, we repeated our ACR experiments and tested shock-odor avoidance first in the absence of stimulation and then re-tested the same flies again after neuronal silencing. As observed in the screen experiment previously (Figure 3A), optogenetic inhibition during agitation and the first 10s of the post-agitation test strongly impaired shock-odor avoidance and locomotion. Odor avoidance in the absence of light stimulation was not affected (Figure 5A-C).

Locomotion and odor avoidance are modulated by distinct forms of arousal

The driver *R13D11-G4* (Figure S2D) captures a different set of leg mechanosensory neurons that compare touch and proprioception³⁹. Optogenetic activation of these neurons with Chr induced a brief locomotor response (Figure 4F), however, the shock-odor avoidance remained low after stimulation (Figure 4D-E). Furthermore, we confirmed that optogenetic inhibition of neurons captured by *R13D11-G4* reduces locomotion but it does not impair post-agitation shock-odor avoidance (Figure 5D-F). These data indicate that locomotion and odor memory could be modulated by different arousal pathways.

A sparse population of mechanosensory neurons modulates arousal-induced odor avoidance

The third class of neurons to receive direct input from leg bristles compares stimuli from touch receptors on the same leg³⁹ and is captured by the driver *R69C05-G4* (Figure S2B). Similar to *R18G08-G4*, optogenetically activating *R69C05-G4* neurons rescued shock-odor avoidance (Figure 4G-H) and induced locomotion (Figure 4I). The expression pattern of *R69C05-G4* is localized to a handful of cells in the first and third VNC neuromere as well as the neuropil around the AMMC⁶² (Figure S2B and G). The inhibition of neurons captured by *R69C05-G4* substantially impaired post-agitation odor avoidance (Figure 5G-H) and locomotion (Figure 5I). Taken together, these data suggest that activation of distinct leg sensilla neurons is sufficient to elicit conditioned shock-odor avoidance and optogenetic inhibition of the same neurons is sufficient to impair the agitation-associated increase in shock-odor avoidance.

Figure 4: Optogenetic activation of distinct leg somatosensory neurons improves conditioned odor avoidance

A-C. Brief optogenetic activation of *R18G08-G4* neurons by Chr immediately before the pre-agitation test strongly rescued conditioned odor avoidance in the absence of agitation (A-B). Agitation further increased the performance of *R18G08>Chr* flies by Δ PI +0.1 (B). Activation of leg mechanosensory neurons recapitulated the increase in locomotion that was observed with agitation. *R18G08-G4>Chr* test $n = 300$ flies over 25 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4>Chr* controls $n = 528$ flies over 44 experimental iterations. **D-F.** Activation of leg mechanosensory neurons captured by *R13D11-G4* did not improve odor avoidance (D-E), however, activation did produce a brief increase in locomotion (F). *R13D11-G4>Chr* test $n = 312$ flies over 26 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4>Chr* controls $n = 336$ flies over 28 experimental iterations. **G-I.** Similar to *R18G08-G4*, activation of leg mechanosensory neurons with *R69C05-G4* substantially improved odor avoidance in the absence of agitation (G-H) and increased locomotion (I). *R69C05-G4>Chr* test $n = 216$ flies over 18 experimental iterations. *R69C05-G4>Chr* controls $n = 408$ flies over 34 experimental iterations. For all panels the same dataset as shown in Figure 3E was used for analyses. Additional statistics are presented in Supplementary Table [ST1](#).

Figure 5: Transient inhibition of leg somatosensory neurons impairs memory retrieval

A-C. Inhibition of *R18G08-G4* neurons with ACR during the second agitation test strongly impaired shock-odor avoidance (A-B). Actuation of *R18G08* neurons also strongly impaired the post-agitation locomotor response (C). *R18G08-G4>ACR* test $n = 336$ flies over 28 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4>ACR* controls $n = 432$ flies over 36 experimental iterations. The same data was used for analyses in panels A-C. **D-F.** Optogenetic inhibition of leg neurons captured by *R13D11-G4* did not change the post-agitation odor avoidance (D-E) or the locomotor response (F). *R13D11-G4>ACR* test $n = 288$ flies over 24 experimental iterations. *R18G08-G4>ACR* controls $n = 444$ flies over 37 experimental iterations. The same data was used for analyses in panels D-F. **G-I.** Inhibition of leg mechanosensory neurons with *R69C05-G4>ACR* strongly impaired the post-agitation odor avoidance (G-H) and locomotor responses (I). *R69C05-G4>ACR* test $n = 253$ flies over 23 experimental iterations. *R69C05-G4>ACR* controls $n = 432$ flies over 36 experimental iterations. The same data was used for analyses in panels G-I. Additional numerical statistics are presented in Supplementary Table [ST1](#).

Locomotor activity at the start of pre-agitation test predicts shock-odor avoidance

Locomotion is regarded as a marker of overall arousal and in our experiments, in general, an increase in locomotion coincided with an increase in conditioned odor avoidance (Figures 2 and 3). One notable exception is our experiment with *R13D11-G4*, where optogenetic actuation substantially affected locomotion but did not change shock-odor avoidance (Figures 4 and 5, panels D-F). To test whether locomotor activity correlates with PI, we combined the data from all foregoing experiments and plotted the average speed versus the average corresponding PI during pre- and post-agitation test epochs. We observed a strong correlation between fly speed at the beginning of the pre-agitation test and PI assessed at a later time point ($R^2 = 0.45$, Figure 6A). However, the average speed midway (Figure 6B) testing showed only a negligible trend with PI ($R^2 = 0.09$, Figure 6B). In addition, fly speed at the start of the post-agitation test did not correlate with PI ($R^2 = 0$, Figure 6C) and a negligible negative trend was observed between fly speed midway testing and post-agitation test PI ($R^2 = 0.08$, Figure 6D). In summary, these data suggest that fly speed at the start of the pre-agitation test can partially predict how well flies will avoid the shock-odor and therefore act as a marker of memory-relevant arousal.

Figure 6: Increased fly speed at the start of pre-agitation test correlates with a higher PI

A. The panel shows the average speed of *Drosophila* during the first 10s of pre-agitation test plotted against the respective average PI during the last 30s of testing. Flies that were active at the start of testing showed higher odor avoidance during the later assessment period: $R^2 = 0.45$ (95%CI = + 0.29, +0.6). **B.** Average fly speed during the middle phase of pre-agitation test (60-70s into the testing epoch) did not correlate with odor avoidance (assessed during the last 30s of the testing period). $R^2 = 0.09$ (95%CI = - 0.02, +0.2). **C.** Average fly speed during the first 10s of the post-agitation test did not correlate with shock-odor avoidance. $R^2 = 0$ (95%CI = - 0.02, +0.03). **D.** Average fly speed during the middle phase of the post-agitation test did not correlate with odor avoidance during testing. $R^2 = 0.08$ (95%CI = - 0.03, +0.18). For all panels a combined sample size of $n = 15145$ flies was used, consisting of 86 individual experiments. The data used for correlation analyses was derived from preceding MOT conditioning experiments (Figures 2-5 and Supplementary Figure 2D). Each dot represents one experiment. Additional statistics are presented in Supplementary Table ST1.

Activation of dopaminergic protocerebral anterior medial neurons improves odor avoidance

To elicit odor avoidance behavior, the arousal stimulus must be integrated with valent odor memory information that is mediated by the Kenyon cells of the *Drosophila* mushroom bodies (MB) ^{63,64}. The Kenyon cells are innervated by different clusters of dopaminergic neurons (DANs) and the protocerebral anterior medial (PAM) ⁶⁵ cluster has been previously implicated in a variety of arousal-mediated behaviors ^{23,66-72}. To test whether PAM actuation modulates arousal-dependent shock-odor avoidance, we optogenetically activated different PAM subsets immediately before the pre-agitation test (Figure S3). Activating the majority of PAM neurons with *R58E02-G4* substantially improved odor avoidance during pre-agitation testing (Figure S3A-B) and increased locomotion (Figure S3C). The PAM driver *MB042B-G4* captures many of the same neurons as *R58E02-G4* but excludes those that innervate the MB β 2 lobe and peduncle. Activating PAM DANs with *MB042B-G4* produced only a marginal increase in pre-agitation odor avoidance and locomotion (Figure S3D-F). Moreover, activating PAM DANs with *R48B04-G4* - another broad PAM driver, did not change shock-odor avoidance or locomotion (Figure S3G-I). PAM activation with restrictive driver lines such as *MB32B-G4* or *MB56B-G4* also failed to elicit shock-odor avoidance or increase locomotor activity (Figure S3J-O). These data suggest that broad activation of PAM neurons improves shock-odor avoidance and increases activity, whereas activation of more restrictive PAM subsets is not sufficient to elicit shock-odor avoidance.

Figure S3: Broad activation of PAM DANs improves shock-odor avoidance in the absence of agitation

A-C. Optogenetic activation of PAM neurons with *R58E02-G4>Chr* immediately before the pre-agitation test improved conditioned odor avoidance (A-B) and increased locomotion

(C). *R58E02-G4>CsChr* test n = 396 flies over 33 experimental iterations. *R58E02-G4>CsChr* controls n = 204 flies over 17 experimental iterations. Same data was used for analysis in panels A-C. **D-F.** Activation of PAM neurons with *MB042B>Chr* improved conditioned odor avoidance during pre-agitation test (D-E) and increased locomotion (F). *MB42B-G4>CsChr* test n = 516 flies over 43 experimental iterations. *MB42B-G4>CsChr* controls n = 780 flies over 65 experimental iterations. Same data was used for analysis in panels D-F. **G-I.** Activation of PAM neurons with *R48B04>Chr* did not change conditioned odor avoidance (G-H) and produced only a marginal increase in locomotion (I). *R48B04-G4>CsChr* test n = 216 flies over 18 experimental iterations. *R48B04-G4>CsChr* controls n = 444 flies over 37 experimental iterations. Same data was used for analysis in panels G-I. **J-L.** Activation of PAM- $\beta'2$ neurons captured by *MB032B-G4>Chr* had no effect on shock-odor avoidance (J-K) and locomotion (L). *MB032B-G4>CsChr* test n = 276 flies over 23 experimental iterations. *MB32B-G4>CsChr* controls n = 672 flies over 56 experimental iterations. Same data was used for analysis in panels J-L. **M-O.** Similar to *MB032B-G4*, activation of PAM- $\beta'2$ neurons with *MB056B-G4>Chr* did not change shock-odor avoidance (M-N) and locomotion during pre-agitation testing (O). *MB056B-G4>CsChr* test n = 576 flies over 48 experimental iterations. *MB56B-G4>CsChr* controls n = 852 flies over 71 experimental iterations. Same data was used for analysis in panels M-O. In all panels PAM neurons were actuated with a 3 s light pulse prior to the pre-agitation test. Error bars show 95% CI. Additional statistics are presented in Supplementary Table [ST1](#).

Inhibition of PAM activity impairs post-agitation odor avoidance and locomotion

We next tested whether PAM DAN activity is required for the agitation-induced increase in shock-odor avoidance. We screened a selection of PAM driver lines (Figure 7A) where neuronal activity was optogenetically silenced by ACR throughout testing (Figure 7B). Strong reductions in post-agitation odor avoidance were observed with the *R48B04-G4* and *MB056B-G4* driver lines and more modest effects were also observed with *MB042B-G4* and *MB441B-G4* (Figure 7B). *R48B04-G4* and *MB042B-G4* capture relatively broad and largely similar PAM subsets, whereas *MB056B-G4* captures PAM neurons that innervate the $\beta'2$ MB zone and *MB441B-G4* captures neurons that innervate the $\gamma3$ zone (Figure 7A). To verify the screen results we repeated the experiments and tested the flies twice, first in the presence of light stimulation during agitation and immediate testing and then without light stimulation. ACR actuation with *R48B04-G4* led to a strong reduction in post-agitation shock-odor avoidance ($-0.45\Delta\text{PI}$) that was partially restored ($+0.2\Delta\text{PI}$) when the flies were retested in the absence of light stimulation (Figure 7C-D). PAM inhibition with *R48B04-G4* also reduced post-agitation locomotion for the remainder of the experiment (Figure 7E). Re-examining *MB056B-G4>ACR* flies in the same manner as above revealed a strong reduction in shock-odor avoidance after light stimulation ($-0.34\Delta\text{PI}$), that was partially rescued ($+0.16\Delta\text{PI}$) during no light retest (Figure 7F-G). However, ACR stimulation of MB056B PAM neurons did not impair post-agitation locomotor activity (Figure 7H). Taken together, these data suggest that broad activation of PAM neurons is sufficient to induce locomotor activity and improve shock-odor avoidance in the absence of agitation (Figure S3A-F). Conversely, broad inhibition of PAM DANs reduces post-agitation shock-odor

avoidance and locomotion (Figure 7B-E). By targeting specific PAM subsets we have shown that the inhibitory effect is largely mediated by PAM DANs that project to the β '2 MB lobe region (Figure 7F-G), however, optogenetic activation of this PAM subset is not sufficient to elicit shock-odor avoidance.

Figure 7: Inhibition of PAM-cluster neurons during agitation and initial testing impairs conditioned odor avoidance

A. A schematic representation of PAM-MB projection patterns for driver lines used in the screen. PAM projections to the different MB lobe zones are indicated in blue. **B.** Summary of the inhibitory PAM driver screen where the post-agitation shock-odor avoidance comparison between the test (green) and the respective genotypic control flies (gray) is shown. Optogenetic inhibition of PAM activity was achieved by ACR actuation throughout both testing epochs (schematic on top). The strongest impairment effects were observed with the driver lines *R48B04-G4>ACR* and *MB056B-G4>ACR*. *R48B04-G4>ACR* test n = 216 flies over 18 experimental iterations. *R48B04-G4>ACR* controls n = 408 flies over 34 experimental iterations. *MB056B-G4>ACR* test n = 252 flies over 21 experimental iterations. *MB056B-G4>ACR* controls n = 588 flies over 49 experimental iterations. *MB042B-G4>ACR* test n = 168 flies over 14 experimental iterations. *MB042B-G4>ACR* controls n = 444 flies over 37 experimental iterations. *MB441B-G4>ACR* test n = 240 flies

over 20 experimental iterations. *MB441B-G4>ACR* controls n = 264 flies over 22 experimental iterations. *MB032B-G4>ACR* test n = 324 flies over 27 experimental iterations. *MB032B-G4>ACR* controls n = 540 flies over 44 experimental iterations. *R58E02-G4>ACR* test n = 180 flies over 15 experimental iterations. *R58E02-G4>ACR* controls n = 384 flies over 32 experimental iterations. *MB312B-G4>ACR* test n = 180 flies over 15 experimental iterations. *MB312B-G4>ACR* controls n = 228 flies over 19 experimental iterations. *MB196B-G4>ACR* test n = 108 flies over 9 experimental iterations. *MB196B-G4>ACR* controls n = 144 flies over 12 experimental iterations. *MB315C-G4>ACR* test n = 168 flies over 14 experimental iterations. *MB315C-G4>ACR* controls n = 264 flies over 22 experimental iterations. *MB213B-G4>ACR* test n = 192 flies over 16 experimental iterations. *MB213B-G4>ACR* controls n = 312 flies over 26 experimental iterations. **C-E.** Optogenetic inhibition of PAM neurons with *R48B04-G4>ACR* impaired post-agitation odor avoidance. Shock-odor avoidance was tested twice - first after opsin actuation (post-agitation test) and then again in the absence of light stimulation (post-agitation retest, see schematic on top, C). Shock-odor avoidance increased during retest in the absence of ACR actuation (D). *R48B04>ACR* actuation reduced post-agitation locomotion (E). The same data was used for analyses in panels C-E. *R48B04-G4>ACR1* test n = 330 flies over 27 experimental iterations. *R48B04-G4>ACR1* controls n = 396 flies over 33 experimental iterations. **F-H.** PAM inhibition with *MB056B-G4>ACR* impaired post-agitation odor avoidance (F). Retesting the flies in the absence of light stimulation restored shock-odor avoidance (G). PAM inhibition captured by *MB056B-G4* did not change post-agitation locomotion (H). The same data was used for analyses in panels F-H. *MB056B-G4>ACR1* test n = 252 flies over 21 experimental iterations. *MB056B-G4>ACR1* controls n = 300 flies over 25 experimental iterations. Additional statistics are presented in Supplementary Table [ST1](#).

Mechanosensory induction of shock-odor avoidance requires PAM activity

Our studies have shown that arousal-induced shock-odor avoidance can be manipulated in various ways by targeting different neuronal subsets that are presumably involved in arousal processing (Figures 3 and 7). As the final step of this investigation we asked whether mechanosensory transduction mediated by leg sensilla and the effects mediated by PAM neurons are part of the same arousal processing pathway. To this end we optogenetically activated leg sensilla neurons with *R18G08>Chr* in the presence and absence of PAM silencing by *R48B04>ACR*. As observed previously (Figure 4A-C), activation of leg sensilla neurons strongly increased pre-agitation shock-odor avoidance (Figure 8A-B) but had a limited effect on locomotion (Figure 8C), due to the reduced efficacy of Chr actuation by green light⁴⁹. Activation of leg sensilla neurons in the presence of PAM silencing substantially decreased pre-agitation odor avoidance (Figure 8A, $-0.30\Delta\text{PI}$). Taken together, these data suggest that mechanosensory induction of shock-odor avoidance is partially dependant of PAM activity.

D Odor avoidance induction by arousal

Figure 8: PAM activity is partially required for mechanosensory induction of odor avoidance

A-C. Brief activation of leg sensilla neurons with *R18G08>Chr* increased pre-agitation test shock-odor avoidance (A-B). This effect was substantially reduced in the presence of PAM neuron silencing by *R48B04-G4>ACR*. Activation of leg sensilla neurons modestly increased locomotion, however, this effect was less pronounced in the presence of PAM neuron silencing (C). The same data was used for analyses in panels F-H.

R18G08-LexA>Chr; R48B04-G4>ACR n = 468 flies over 39 experimental iterations.

R18G08-LexA>Chr; R48B04-G4 n = 444 flies over 37 experimental iterations. Error bars show 95% CI. Additional numerical statistics are presented in Supplementary Table [ST1](#).

D. Schematic of the arousal-mediated shock-odor avoidance induction pathway. External stimuli that modulate the arousal state of the animal are labeled as “inputs” in red, whereas neuronal circuits that process information and are modulated by arousal are displayed as “processors” in green. Behavioral “output” of the animal is shown in black. Arousal is proposed to play a “transistor” function that amplifies behavioral output such as shock-odor avoidance and activity.

Discussion

Arousal modulates selective attention and memory across organisms

The state of arousal is regulated by hormones and neurotransmitters in accordance with physiological feedback (endogenous arousal) and stimuli from the environment (exogenous arousal) ⁷. Studies in vertebrates have mostly focused on the role of endogenous arousal in modulating behaviors while the role of exogenous arousal remains poorly understood. In rodents and humans, arousing stimuli have been found to release norepinephrine and dopamine into the amygdala, which in turn enhances processes in the hippocampus and other memory-relevant areas of the brain (reviewed in ^{8,73,74}). Human emotions have been shown to increase endogenous arousal and amplify the perception of a salient stimulus. When different stimuli are presented at the same time or in quick succession, high levels of endogenous arousal amplify the perception of a salient stimulus and impair perception of the less salient stimulus ⁷⁵. In addition to modulating selective attention ^{1,30}, endogenous arousal has also been shown to increase memory consolidation ^{8,9,76,77}. Although various models of how endogenous arousal could modulate stimulus perception and memory have been proposed (reviewed in ⁷⁸), there is no unified theory to date. Arousal studies in *Drosophila* have primarily been focused on exogenous arousal, induced via mechanical agitation. High levels of arousal in *Drosophila* are associated with various changes in behavior, such as a general increase in activity ⁷, reduced sleep ¹³, startle-induced hyperactivity ⁴, increased foraging behavior ¹⁸ and courtship ⁷⁹. Our study shows that arousal also elicits the display of associative odor memory.

Arousal is required for the display of odor avoidance behavior in *Drosophila*

Our study revealed that *Drosophila* display low shock-odor avoidance after conditioning if agitation or other sources of arousal are omitted (Figures 1, 2 and S1). In this study, it was not feasible to directly measure neural correlates of arousal by electrophysiological recordings during conditioning ^{3,80}. However, by using locomotion, as a proxy for general arousal levels (Figure 2D), we can speculate that arousal levels are high at the start of conditioning and throughout shock training. After unpaired odor presentation, arousal levels decline and remain low during pre-agitation testing. Applying an acute arousal stimulus in the form of agitation almost immediately improves shock-odor avoidance (Figure 2C). A chronic arousal stimulus, e.g. in the form of hunger also improves odor avoidance in the absence of agitation, but it does not further improve the performance of already agitated flies (Figure S1D-F). Arousal does not appear to be required immediately after training. In fact, flies aroused 45 min after initial training still show unimpaired shock-odor avoidance (Figure 1G). Overall, these data suggest that a state of high arousal is required for the display of odor memory.

Arousal-induced activity at the start of testing partially predicts shock-odor avoidance

The most apparent effect of arousal on fly behavior is the increase in activity that coincides with an increase in shock-odor avoidance (Figure 2C-D). Although activity is often used as a marker of general arousal levels ¹¹, studies have shown that behaviors are controlled by different forms of arousal ⁴. In addition, we also identified instances where modulation of locomotor activity did not affect shock-odor avoidance (e.g. Figure 4D-F, Figure 8A-C), therefore the relationship between locomotion and shock-odor avoidance was unclear. Our

correlation analyses (Figure 6) confirmed that increased fly activity at the start of testing partially predicts increased performance later on (Figure 6A, $R^2 = 0.45$). Surprisingly, this relationship was only true for a narrow time window at the beginning of testing, as locomotion did not correlate with odor avoidance PI at any other point during the testing period. These data indicate that locomotion and a high state of arousal are primarily required during the initial phase of testing, when flies make a directional choice.

Sensory neurons modulate shock-odor avoidance

We performed an anatomical screen to identify neuropil regions and circuits that mediate agitation-induced shock-odor avoidance. Optogenetic activation with *NompC-G4* and *Nan-G4* driver lines that capture mechanosensory cells improved shock-odor avoidance in the absence of agitation while inhibition impaired shock-odor avoidance after agitation (Figure 3). Leg bristle actuation has recently been implicated in locomotor activity induction⁶¹ and focusing on somatosensory neurons, we tested circuits that have been shown to receive direct input from leg sensilla³⁹. The three driver lines (*R69C05-G4*, *R13D11-Gal4* and *R18G08-G4*) capture different neuron classes and optogenetically manipulating two of the classes was sufficient to either elicit or impair shock-odor avoidance (Figures 4 and 5). The driver *R69C05-G4* is of particular interest because it captures only a handful of neurons in the VNC and has a relatively sparse expression pattern in the brain (Figure S2B). Overall, our data suggest that memory-relevant mechanosensory arousal stimuli are initially detected by neurons in the VNC and future experiments could employ intersectional strategies to identify downstream circuits involved in arousal stimulus propagation.

PAM activity is required for agitation-induced odor avoidance

Several studies have shown that arousal is sensitive to perturbations in dopamine signaling^{4,11,28,81,82} and PAM⁸³ DANs have previously been implicated in state-dependent behavior²⁸, such as startle-induced locomotion⁷⁰, appetitive memory^{66,67,84}, valence⁶⁹, foraging⁸⁵ and others⁸⁶. The present study revealed that broad inhibition of PAM DANs with *R48B04>ACR* is sufficient to impair post-agitation odor avoidance and locomotion (Figure 7B-E). Furthermore, we identified a specific PAM cluster that innervates the $\beta'2$ area of the MB lobes to be primarily responsible for the inhibitory effect. Inhibition of $\beta'2$ PAM neurons with two different driver lines (*MB032B-G4* and *MB056B-G4*; Figure 7B, F-H) was sufficient to partially impair post-agitation shock-odor avoidance. The $\beta'2m$ neurons have been previously implicated in appetitive conditioning⁸⁷, wakefulness⁸⁸, movement⁸⁹ and other behaviors²⁸. Since all of these behaviors are in some form modulated by arousal, it is conceivable that $\beta'2$ DANs could play a role as an arousal state modulator. Besides *R58E02-G4* and *MB042B-G4*, which both capture broad PAM subsets (Figure 7A), optogenetic activation with other broad (e.g. *R48B04-G4*) or specific drivers did not elicit shock-odor avoidance (Figure S3) or locomotion. Taken together, these data suggest that PAM DANs are partially required for arousal-mediated retrieval of odor memory, however, whether PAM activation can also be instructive is unclear.

Mechanosensory induction of shock-odor avoidance partially requires PAM activity

Numerous studies have shown that odor memory information is encoded within the Kenyon cells of the *Drosophila* MB, however, how memory information intersects with the arousal state of the fly is insufficiently understood. Our screening experiments identified mechanosensory neurons and PAM DANs as the main suppressors of agitation-induced shock-odor avoidance. Furthermore, we observed that avoidance induction via the activation of mechanosensory neurons was less effective when coupled with PAM silencing (Figure 8A-B). These data indicate PAM DANs and leg mechanosensors could be part of the same mechanosensory arousal processing pathway. To further investigate this relationship, follow-up studies could employ life imaging techniques to test whether PAM activity is modulated by mechanosensory stimulation.

Conclusions

The majority of olfactory memory studies in *Drosophila* have been performed by using the classical T-maze conditioning protocol³⁸ which includes agitation. Our study shows that the agitation step is a critical component of conditioned odor avoidance behavior. Agitation elicits arousal that is initially detected by leg mechanosensors and leads to an increase in activity. Optogenetic activation of leg mechanosensors is sufficient to elicit conditioned odor avoidance and partially requires the activity of dopaminergic PAM neurons in the fly brain. Our study identifies arousal as a critical component of aversive olfactory conditioning and identifies circuits for further investigations into arousal-mediated memory retrieval.

Methods

***Drosophila* husbandry**

Flies were raised on standard cornmeal-based food medium containing 1.25 % w/v agar, 10.5 % w/v dextrose, 10.5 % w/v maize and 2.1 % w/v yeast. For optogenetic experiments, *Drosophila* were reared in the dark and placed on food which contained all-trans retinal (ATR) for three days prior to conditioning experiments as previously described⁴⁰.

***Drosophila* stocks**

The *R55B01-G4* stock was provided by Richard Benton (University of Lausanne) and has been previously described in⁵¹. The *UAS-ACR* stock has been previously described⁴⁰. The *TH-G4*⁹⁰, *c061-G4*⁴⁷, *kras-G4*⁴⁷ and *NPF-G4*⁹¹ stocks were provided by Scott Waddell (University of Oxford). All other stocks have been obtained from the Bloomington *Drosophila* Research Center (BDSC) and are summarized in [Supplementary Table 2](#).

Olfactory conditioning in the T-maze: Classic protocol

Olfactory conditioning was performed in the T-maze apparatus according to the Classic protocol⁹² (Figure 1A). Newly eclosed flies were collected into vials in batches of 40–60 in an approximately even gender ratio and left to recover from CO₂ anesthesia for at least 1 day before being used in conditioning experiments. On the day of testing, approximately 60 flies were transferred into a vial containing a piece of wet filter paper and left to rest for about 1 hr. To begin the experiment, the flies were tapped into the T-maze elevator and subsequently into the training tube which contained a copper grid electrode (Figure 1A, top row). During a training cycle, air (187 ml/min) was presented for 90 s, following which, either 3-octanol (OCT) or 4-methylcyclohexanol (MCH) was presented for 60 s, along with

12 electric shocks at 60 V. After presenting air for another 60 s, the opposite odor was presented for the same duration followed by air for 90 s. The flies were initially left to recover in the chambers for about 30 s during the 90 s-long air phase. Subsequently, they were tapped back into the elevator, which was then pushed near the choice point between the two lower arms of the T-maze. At the end of the second air phase, clear plastic tubes were connected to the lower T-maze arms. At the beginning of the testing phase, the elevator was pushed to the choice point, thus releasing the flies between the MCH and OCT tubes for 2 min before the elevator was raised again to separate the two tubes. The number of flies in each tube was used to calculate the PI as described previously⁹².

Variant T-maze protocols

In No change and Circulated protocols, training and testing were carried out in copper grid-lined tubes. At the start of the experiment, the tubes were attached to the lower T-maze arms (Figure 1B).

No change protocol. The flies were trained in two copper-grid tubes plugged into the choice-point ports. After conditioning, flies were left in the tubes for the normal wait time, without any transfer or agitation.

Circulated protocol. Training and testing were done in the grid-line tubes at the choice-point ports as in the No change protocol, but with the addition of an elevator transfer between testing and training. After training, the flies were first tapped into one of the tubes, which was then relocated to the upper position from where the flies were tapped into the elevator. For testing, the elevator with flies was pushed down to the choice point and the flies were allowed to roam for 2 min before the elevator column was raised to separate the two tubes, as in the Classic protocol.

Reduced light and sound protocol. To suppress light and noise, the classic protocol was performed in a dark room to eliminate visual cues, with the T-maze tapped against a padded surface during the elevator transfer step to reduce noise cues.

Added light and sounds protocol. To add light and noise to the No change protocol, the T-maze containing the conditioned flies was taken out of the incubator and placed gently on the bench for 30s to be exposed to room light. Next to it, a second, empty T-maze was tapped in a similar manner during elevator transfer to mimic the sound stimulus.

Shaking protocol. Flies were conditioned with the No-change method and the T-maze was either agitated immediately before testing or the flies were left in the T-maze chambers for 45 min and then agitated before test and evaluation.

Multi-fly olfactory training (MOT) chambers

The chambers of the MOT apparatus have been described previously⁴⁰. Briefly, the behavioral arena of each chamber was 50 mm long, 5 mm wide and 1.3 mm high. The floor and ceiling of each chamber was composed of a glass slide printed with transparent indium tin oxide electrodes (Walthy; China). Clean, compressed air was used to carry the odors into the chamber via vents on each side; air exited the chamber through vents located in the center of the chamber.

MOT conditioning

The MOT assay, previously described by ⁴⁰, was designed to permit the monitoring and real-time evaluation of *Drosophila* behavior throughout aversive olfactory conditioning. Unlike the T-maze, flies in the MOT are trained and tested in the same chamber. The full MOT conditioning protocol is outlined in Figure 2B. At the start of each experiment, *Drosophila* were anesthetized on ice and loaded into the MOT chambers. If not otherwise indicated, each experiment was performed with six flies per chamber. A schematic of the MOT2 apparatus is presented in Figure 2A. Chambers were illuminated from the bottom by infrared LEDs. Olfactory preference was measured by tracking the movement of individual flies and scored automatically by using the in-house CRITTA tracking programme ⁹³. Fly behavior was recorded with an AVT F-080 guppy camera that was connected to a video acquisition board (PCI-1409, National Instruments). Flies were conditioned using electric shock (12 electric shocks at 60 V) that was delivered when the animals came in contact with the floor and ceiling. A standard conditioning cycle lasted for 12 min and followed the sequence shown in Figure 2B. At the start of each trial, flies were placed in the chambers and were given 60 s to acclimatize in pure air; one half of the chamber was exposed to MCH while the other half to OCT for 60 s during the bias test. After another 120 s of pure air, the whole arena was exposed for 60 s to the conditioned odor in the presence of shock. This was followed by 120 s of air and the exposure of the whole arena to the second odor for 60 s in the absence of shock. After a 120 s clean air epoch, odor preference was tested for 120 s by exposing one side of the arena to the shock-associated odor and the other side to the neutral odor, during the pre-agitation test. After a brief wait, the flies were agitated either with tapping the chamber or using air puffs, depending on the apparatus version (described in detail below). Following agitation, flies were subjected to a second odor-preference epoch, during the post-agitation test.

MOT versions and agitation

Two versions of the MOT were used in this study. In MOT version 1, four chambers were mounted on a previously described single-fly olfactory training device ²² with windows and 45° mirrors in the chambers to allow the camera to image groups of flies from above. Conditioning was done as described above, with agitation delivered by removing the chambers and tapping for 5–10 s; removal and replacement took a total of ~30 s. In MOT version 2, the chamber dimensions were retained, and integrated into a flat design that allowed camera imaging from above and top-down optogenetic illumination (45° angle) (Figure 2A). The number of chambers was increased from four to ten. For MOT version 2, a high-pressure air line (20 PSI) was added that allowed 7 s of agitation with a sequence of 5 air puffs at a 2 L/min flow rate, which was sufficient to reliably push the flies around the chamber into the middle. The intervals between the pre-agitation and post-agitation tests in MOT1 and MOT2 were ~30 s and 8 s, respectively.

Estimation of fly activity in the MOT

Fly activity calculations were based on x and y MOT arena position coordinates logged by CRITTA in real time at 1 or 25 frames per second (FPS). Activity was routinely monitored throughout the experiment. Raw velocity values in pixel/s were converted into mm/s values and averaged into 1FPS bins where required. The raw data was filtered and pixel/s values

>60 were discarded in order to remove ID swaps. Afterwards, speed data were averaged between chambers with flies of the same genotype and number across at experimental iterations and plotted with a 95% CI ribbon with custom Python (Python Software Foundation) scripts.

Olfactometer

Odors were delivered as previously described²². Dry, compressed air was routed through mass flow controllers (MFC; Sensirion AG, Switzerland). Carrier air flow was controlled with two 2 L/min capacity MFCs and pushed through a humidifying gas washing bottle containing distilled water (Schott Duran) at 0.6 L/min. odor streams were controlled with 500 ml/min MFCs and pushed through glass vials containing pure liquid odorants: MCH and OCT. odor administration was carried out with the following MFC settings: OCT left side 60-70 ml/min; OCT right side 60-70 ml/min; MCH left side 130-150 ml/min; MCH right side 140-160 ml/min. odor presentation at the behavioral chamber arms was switched with computer controlled solenoid valves (The Lee Company, USA). The left and right olfactometer arms were connected to either the T-maze or the MOT apparatus for air/odor mixtures to be delivered. The MFCs were regulated via CRITTA custom LabVIEW code and measured with a photoionization detector (PID, RAE systems; PGM-7340). T-maze experiments were carried out at odor concentrations of 25-32 ppm for MCH and 5-10 ppm for OCT, as measured with an isobutanol-calibrated PID. MOT experiments were performed with a relative concentration of 10 -14 ppm for MCH and 14-18 ppm for OCT in the chambers. odor concentrations were routinely measured in an *ad hoc* manner before the start of experiments and in between conditioning trials. Before each experiment, control trials with wild type flies were run to ensure optimal calibration of the MOT apparatus.

Optogenetics

Neuronal activation with Chr⁴⁹ was achieved with red LED light at 617 nm and 24 $\mu\text{W}/\text{mm}^2$ intensity. If not otherwise indicated, flies were briefly exposed to red light immediately before the pre-agitation test. Neuronal inhibition with ACR was achieved by using green LED light at 530 nm with 58 $\mu\text{W}/\text{mm}^2$ intensity. All flies used for optogenetic experiments were kept in the dark and were reared on standard fly food which was supplemented with all trans-Retinal (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) as previously described⁴⁰.

Calculation of performance indices

The performance index in the T-maze was calculated as previously described⁹². PI in the MOT was calculated with the same formula; however, instead of a single endpoint, the counting was performed on individual video frames over time. This temporally-resolved PI score was calculated by counting the number of flies in each odor-covered area during the last 30 s of each testing epoch for each chamber and odor pair. The average performance of flies in each chamber was visualized as a bar chart and a contrast with a 95% CI error envelope presenting a ΔPI . Where applicable, a paired comparison between pre- and post-agitation performance was made.

Starvation

Starved *Drosophila* were kept on 2% agarose (w/v) for either 24 h or 40 h before conditioning.

Neuroanatomy

Adult fly brains were dissected in cold phosphate buffer saline (PBS) and fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 30 min at room temperature. After five 20 min washes with PBT (PBS with 1% Triton X-100 at pH 7.2), samples were blocked in 5% normal goat serum and subsequently incubated with primary antibodies at 4°C overnight. After a set of additional five 20-min washes in PBT, the brains were incubated with secondary antibodies at 4°C overnight. A mouse anti-DLG1 (4F3 anti-Discs large 1, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, 1:200 dilution) primary antibody⁹⁴ and a corresponding secondary antibody conjugated with the mouse-Alexa Fluor 568 (A-11004, Molecular Probes, 1:200 dilution) were used to stain neuropils. For mCD8-GFP detection, an Alexa Fluor 488 rabbit anti-GFP-IgG (A-21311, Molecular Probes, 1:200 dilution) antibody was used. After five 20-min washes with PBT and additional five 20-min washes in PBS, immunolabeled brains were mounted in Vectashield (Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA, USA) and visualized using a Zeiss LSM700 confocal microscope at 10x and 40x magnifications respectively. Fly brains were scanned in the Z-dimension at 0.5 µm intervals with 1,024 × 1,024 pixels in the X-Y dimensions.

Data availability

Acknowledgements

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Author Contributions

Conceptualization: SO, ACC; Methodology: SO, JCS, ACC; Experiments: SO, XYZ; Software: SO (Python), TT (Python), JCS (LabView); Data Analysis: SO; Hardware: SO, JCS, TT; Writing – Original Draft: SO; Writing – Revision: SO, ACC; Visualization: SO, ACC; Supervision: ACC; Project Administration: ACC; Funding Acquisition: ACC.

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